

DETERMINATION OF FORMATION CONSTANTS OF TERNARY COMPLEXES OF BIVALENT METAL IONS CONTAINING ACETYL ACETONE BIVALENT METAL IONS AND FEW ALIPHATIC O-O DONORS

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Formation constants of ternary complexes of bivalent metal ions with oxygen donor (Acetyl acetone) as primary ligand in presence of few O-O donors (viz., Oxalic acid, Malonic acid, Succinic acid, Glutaric acid, Adipic acid, Maleic acid, Fumaric acid, Iminodiacetic acid, hydroxyethyliminodiacetic acid and nitrilotriacetic acid) have been determined pH-metrically in aqueous medium at 30⁰C and I = 0.1 M KNO₃

INTRODUCTION :

Acetylacetone, also known as 2,4-pentanedione, is a versatile organic compound with a wide range of applications in various industries. Its significance stems from its ability to act as a building block for synthesizing diverse chemical compounds and its utility as a functional additive in various applications. Acetylacetone readily forms stable coordination complexes with various metal ions. These metal acetylacetonates find applications in catalysis, metal extraction, and metal plating. In mineral processing, for example, acetyl acetone can be used as an extraction solvent. In continuation of our studies[1-4], coordinating abilities of acetyl acetone (AA) with bivalent metal ions in presence of different dicarboxylic acids (viz., Oxalic acid (Ox), Malonic acid (Malo), Succinic acid (Succ), Glutaric acid (Glut), Adipic acid (Adip), Maleic acid (Male), Fumaric acid (Fum), Iminodiacetic acid (IMDA), hydroxyethyliminodiacetic acid (HIMDA) and nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA)) as secondary ligands have been determined pH-metrically in aqueous medium at 30⁰ C and I = 0.1 M KNO₃

EXPERIMENTAL:

Acetylacetone was purchased from Fluka (Switzerland). Unsaturated dicarboxylic acids- Maleic acid, Fumaric acid, were obtained from BDH- E,Merck. The other ligands, IMDA, NTA were from Sigma and HIMDA was from Fluka. The metal salts of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) were of AnalaR Grade. The metal ion solutions were standardized volumetrically by titration with sodium salt of EDTA [5]. Acid dissociation constants of free ligands and formation constants (binary and ternary) of metal complexes were determined pH-metrically, measuring the pH solution containing ligands in absence or in presence of metal ions in 1:1 or 1:1:1 ratio, using Control Dynamics pH-meter filled with Gel filled electrode.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The pH metric curves of ternary systems show an inflection at m=2 followed by another inflection at m=3. This type of inflections suggest the formation of ternary complexes in stepwise manner, in which acetyl acetone binds only after the complete formation of binary 1:1 metal-dicarboxylic acid complexes. The following equations have been derived from the graphs:

But in the case of ternary complexes involving NTA, the first inflection is observed at $m = 3$ and second at $m = 4$ suggesting the following equations:

In either case, dicarboxylic acids are binding to metal ions first (primary ligands) and acetyl acetone later (secondary ligand) to complete the ternary complexes.

TABLE I : LOGARITHMS OF STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF TERNARY COMPLEXES OF ACETYL ACETONE (AA) WITH BIVALENT METAL IONS IN PRESENCE OF DICARBOXYLIC ACIDS

[T = 30°C, I = 0.1M KNO₃ MEDIUM = AQUEOUS]

Systems	Co(II)	Ni(II)	Cu(II)	Zn(II)
OX + AA	4.60 (0.03)	5.17 (0.04)	6.46 (0.02)	4.25 (0.01)
Malo + AA	4.33 (0.02)	4.79 (0.07)	6.35 (0.03)	4.10 (0.09)
Succ + AA	4.31 (0.07)	4.80 (0.02)	6.12 (0.06)	3.87 (0.03)
Glut + AA	4.15 (0.05)	4.77 (0.02)	5.96 (0.08)	3.91 (0.05)
Adip + AA	3.93 (0.03)	4.69 (0.06)	6.01 (0.05)	3.67 (0.05)
Male + AA	4.19 (0.08)	4.79 (0.08)	5.96 (0.06)	3.99 (0.08)
Fum + AA	4.13 (0.02)	4.69 (0.03)	5.91 (0.07)	3.95 (0.02)
IMDA + AA	3.11 (0.01)	3.83 (0.02)	6.06 (0.07)	2.93 (0.03)
HIMDA + AA	3.04 (0.08)	3.61 (0.03)	5.77 (0.05)	2.86 (0.05)
NTA + AA	2.70 (0.03)	3.29 (0.02)	5.20 (0.01)	2.63 (0.08)

The standard deviations are given in parentheses.

AA = Acetyl Acetone, $pK_a = 8.87 \pm 0.05$, $\log K^M_{ML}$ for Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) are 5.02 ± 0.01 , 5.60 ± 0.06 , 7.87 ± 0.01 & 4.76 ± 0.07 respectively.

The stability constants associated with this type of complex formation is calculated using appropriate equations suggested in literature. The $\Delta \log K$ values and %RS values are calculated using the following equations:

$$\Delta \log K = \log K^{MA}_{MAL} - \log K^M_{ML} \quad \text{----- 5}$$

$$\%RS = (\Delta \log K / \log K^M_{ML}) \times 100 \quad \text{----- 6}$$

The obtained stability constant, $\log K$ values (table -1) and $\Delta \log K$ values along with %RS are given in table -2. The $\Delta \log K$ values are found to be usually negative and are often the same as expected statistically in the absence of electrostatic effects [6] or of any specific interactions between the two ligands [7]. The expected statistical factor for these systems, assuming all the metal ions are in octahedral geometry, would be -0.4. If the observed $\Delta \log K$ values are more negative than -0.4, then it is concluded that apart from statistical reasons, there are also some other factors responsible for destabilization.

TABLE II : COMPARISON OF ΔLOGK & %RS VALUES FOR THE TERNARY COMPLEXES OF ACETYL ACETONE WITH BIVALENT METAL IONS IN PRESENCE OF DICARBOXYLIC ACIDS

[T= 30°C, I = 0.1M KNO₃ MEDIUM = AQUEOUS]

Systems	Co(II)	Ni(II)	Cu(II)	Zn(II)
OX + AA	- 0.42 (-8.36)	- 0.43 (-7.67)	-1.41 (-17.91)	- 0.51 (-10.71)
Malo + AA	- 0.69 (-13.74)	- 0.81 (-14.46)	- 1.52 (-19.31)	- 0.66 (-13.86)
Succ + AA	- 0.71 (-14.14)	- 0.80 (-14.28)	- 1.75 (-22.23)	- 0.89 (-18.69)
Glut + AA	- 0.87 (-17.33)	- 0.83 (-14.82)	- 1.91 (-24.26)	- 0.85 (-17.85)
Adip + AA	- 1.09 (-21.71)	- 0.91 (-16.25)	- 1.86 (-23.63)	- 1.09 (-22.89)
Male + AA	- 0.83 (-16.53)	- 0.81 (-14.46)	- 1.91 (-24.46)	- 0.77 (-16.17)
Fum + AA	- 0.89 (-17.72)	- 0.91 (-16.25)	- 1.96 (-24.90)	- 0.81 (-17.01)
IMDA + AA	- 1.91 (-38.04)	- 1.77 (-31.60)	- 1.81 (-22.99)	- 1.83 (-38.44)

HIMDA + AA	- 1.98 (-39.44)	- 1.99 (-35.53)	- 2.10 (-26.68)	- 1.90 (-39.91)
NTA + AA	- 2.32 (-46.21)	- 2.31 (-41.25)	- 2.67 (-33.92)	- 2.13 (-44.74)

% RS values are given in parenthesis

Perusal of $\Delta \log K$ values and %RS values for maleic acid and fumaric acid from table-2, the order of stability is found to be Maleic acid > Fumaric acid. This is attributed to the fact that Maleic acid possesses the double bond which increases the stability of complexes due to exocyclic conjugation. On the other hand, the fumaric acid due to its trans geometry may impart greater strain during chelate formation, so it forms a less stable ternary complex. The destabilization resulting in these complexes is due to i) Statistical reasons ii) trans geometry of fumaric acid which is incapable of strong bidentate mode of binding.

The order of stability (table-2) with respect to primary ligands (viz, IMDA, HIMDA and NTA), found to be IMDA > HIMDA > NTA. The destabilization factors in these systems are: i) Statistical ii) electrostatic repulsion iii) steric hindrance in HIMDA and denticity of ligands. The ligands, IMDA and HIMDA upon coordination with bivalent ions form binary neutral complexes whereas NTA forms mono negative binary complexes. Therefore, more electrostatic repulsions are expected between mono negative acetyl acetone and $[M-NTA]^-$ than between mono negative acetyl acetone and neutral $[M-IMDA]$ or $[M-HIMDA]$ binary complexes. Higher stability of $[Cu-IMDA-AA]$ system than $[Cu-HIMDA-AA]$ - system may be due to steric hindrance caused by β -hydroxyethyl group in HIMDA.

The stability order (table-2) with respect to dicarboxylic acids is, Malo > Ox > Succ > Glu > Adip. This trend is the same as found in their 1:1 binary complexes $[M(II)\text{-Dicarboxylic acids}]$. The ligand acetyl acetone (AA) forms 6 member rings with these metal ions in their binary complexes. Similarly, dicarboxylic acids being bidentate ligands form rings of different sizes. The combination of both ligands (primary and secondary) form different combinations of rings in ternary complexes are as follows: 6 + 5 (AA + Oxo), 6 + 6 (AA + Malo), 6 + 7 (AA + Succ), 6 + 8 (AA + Glut) and 6 + 9 (AA + Adip). The observed trend is in accordance with the rule formulated by Sigel [8,9]. Sigel [10] suggested that ternary complexes containing two different sizes of chelates rings formed by two different ligands, will have stability order as: (5+6) > (6+6) > (5+5) combination. This is due to the fact that strain involved in forming larger ring systems could be more.

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